

Template synthesis of copper(II) complexes of two twelve-membered tetradentate nitrogen donor macrocyclic ligands

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Copper(II) complexes of general composition CuLX_2 (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$, NO_3^- and MeCOO^- ; $\text{L} = \text{DAED}$, BDAP) have been prepared with 2,3,8,9-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene [N_4] (DAED) and 2,3,8,9-tetraphenyl-6,12-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene [N_4] (BDAP). All the complexes exhibit magnetic moment corresponding to one unpaired electron. The complexes have tetragonal geometry except the sulfato complexes, which are five-coordinate square-pyramidal.

The complexes of metal ions with macrocyclic ligands are significant because of their resemblance with many natural systems, such as porphyrins¹ and cobalamines². Many of the transition metal ions in the living systems work as enzymes or carriers in macrocyclic ligand field environment. Therefore, meaningful research in this direction might generate simple models for biologically occurring metalloenzymes³ etc., and thus help us in further understanding of biological systems. These ligands are also of theoretical interest as they are capable of furnishing an environment of controlled geometry and ligand field strength⁴. In the present paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of a series of copper(II) complexes derived from the ligand 2,3,8,9-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene [N_4] (DAED) and 2,3,8,9-tetraphenyl-6,12-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene [N_4] (BDAP).

DAED

BDAP

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) have the general composition Cu(L)X_2 (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, NO_3^- , $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and MeCOO^- ; $\text{L} = \text{DAED}$, BDAP). The molar conductance values ($6\text{--}18 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) show that the complexes are non-electrolytes, thus indicating that the anions are coordinated to the metal ion in these complexes and $[\text{CuLX}_2]$ formula may be suggested for these complexes. Magnetic moments of all the complexes at room temperature ($1.92\text{--}2.02 \text{ B.M.}$)

correspond to one unpaired electron. All the complexes may be considered to have tetragonal geometry, however, sulfato complexes were found to have five-coordinated geometry.

Table 1. Physical and ESR spectral data of the complexes^a

Compd.	Colour (Yield %)	Decomp. temp. °C	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_0	G
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DAED})\text{Cl}_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$	Yellow (77)	130	2.15	2.04	2.07	3.75
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DAED})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	Blue (65)	107	2.26	2.13	2.17	2.00
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DAED})(\text{MeCOO})_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	Violet (40)	123	2.10	2.03	2.05	3.33
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DAED})\text{SO}_4]$ $\text{CuC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{SO}_4$	Blue (72)	114	2.27 (g_3)	2.07 (g_2)	2.06 (g_1)	0.047 (R)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BDAP})\text{Cl}_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$	Blue (73)	140	2.16	2.05	2.08	3.20
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BDAP})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	Violet (67)	105	2.29	2.15	2.19	1.93
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BDAP})(\text{MeCOO})_2]$ $\text{CuC}_{38}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	Black (43)	130	2.05	2.02	2.03	2.50
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BDAP})\text{SO}_4]$ $\text{CuC}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{SO}_4$	Blue (72)	119	2.22 (g_3)	2.04 (g_2)	2.02 (g_1)	0.10 (R)

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory Cu, C, H and N analyses.

$$g_0 = (g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})/3$$

$$G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$$

$$R = (g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_1)$$

IR spectra of all the complexes do not show bands that can be assigned to the C=O or NH_2 groups⁵. The strong bands appearing in the spectra of all the complexes at $1370\text{--}1450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N) indicate the presence of coordinated azomethine group⁶. In the IR spectra of the nitrate complexes bands at $1470\text{--}1390$ and $1340\text{--}1320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ show that nitrate acts as unidentate. The acetato complexes show

bands at 1610–1625 (C=O) and 1305–1320 cm^{-1} (C–O), which indicates that acetate acts as unidentate in complexes⁷. Some new bands appear at 700–900 cm^{-1} , but the assignment is not possible due to complexity of the spectrum due to the overlap of the absorption with imine and CH_2 groups.

The electronic spectra of six-coordinate Cu^{II} complexes have either D_{4h} or C_{4v} symmetry and the E_g and T_{2g} levels of the 2D free ion will split into B_{1g} , A_{1g} , B_{2g} and E_g levels, respectively. Thus three spin-allowed transitions are expected in the visible and near-IR region, but only a few complexes are known⁸ in which such bands are resolved either by Gaussian analysis or by single crystal polarization studies. These bands have been assigned to the following transitions in order of increasing energy : $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_z^2$), $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$) and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$). The energy level sequence will depend on the amount of tetragonal distortion due to ligand field and the Jahn-Teller effect⁹. The electronic spectra of the present complexes show one characteristic band at 10515–14814 cm^{-1} except the acetato complex which shows two characteristic band at 11409 and 17452 cm^{-1} , assigned to the $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ transitions, respectively. The $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ transition is usually not observed as a separate band in tetragonal field. The splitting of the 2E_g state is a measure of the planer and the axial field. Since the planer field is constant in all the present complexes, the change in position of the bands may be due to the axial field only. In the Cu^{II} complexes, the $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ transition is shifted to higher energy, the order being $\text{Cl}^- < \text{NO}_3^- < \text{MeCOO}^-$.

All the complexes show anisotropic ESR spectra characteristic of tetragonal Cu^{II} . The values of g are given in Table 1. The anisotropic g -values have been calculated by the method reported earlier¹⁰.

The stronger interaction along the Z-axis is to be accompanied by an increase in the value of g_{\parallel} . The stronger axial bonding leads to an increase in the length of the bond in the XY-plane, which results in a decrease of both the in-plane covalency and energy of the $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ transition¹¹.

Both these factors tend to increase the value of g_{\parallel} . The g_{\parallel} values for the complexes studied follow the order : $\text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{MeCOO}^-$, which to a great extent is consistent with the positions of the anions in the spectrochemical series¹². Further, in an axial symmetry, the g -values are related by the expression, $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between the copper centres in a

polycrystalline solid. According to Hathaway and Billing¹³, if the value of G is > 4 , the exchange interaction is negligible, while $G < 4$ indicates a considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The calculated G values are presented in Table 1 and are < 4 , suggesting that there is interaction between the copper centres.

Sulfato complexes of ligands :

IR spectra of the complexes show bands corresponding to monodentate sulfate⁷. The bands are observed at ~940, 1040–1060, 1180–1290 and 640 cm^{-1} . Thus, a five-coordinate structure is suggested for these complexes. Two basic structures¹⁴ can be adopted by complexes for coordination number five – trigonal bipyramidal and square-pyramidal. Practically, there appears to be little difference in energy¹⁵ between the two structures. The structures, square-pyramidal and trigonal bipyramidal have the ground state configuration 2B_1 (unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital), and 2A_1 (unpaired electron in the d_z^2 orbital) respectively¹⁶. ESR spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes prove to be good indicators for distinguishing between these two ground states. For system with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$, the ratio¹⁷ $(g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_1)$, called the parameter R , is a very useful parameter for this purpose. If the ground state is predominately 2A_1 , the value of R is > 1 . On the other hand, for the ground state predominately 2B_1 the value of R is < 1 . The complexes under study show the values of R 0.047 and 0.10, to be less than 1, thus indicating 2B_1 as the ground state. Thus for CuLSO_4 , five-coordinate square-pyramidal structures may be suggested.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. DMSO was of spectroscopic grade. The C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Shimadzu 1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded as powder sample at room temperature on a E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the g -marker. Molar conductance (in DMSO) was measured on an Elico CM82T conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a callibrant.

All the complexes were prepared by the template method.

Cu^{II} complexes of DAED : A mixture of ethanolic solution (20 ml) of ethylenediamine (0.002 mol) and conc. (37%) HCl (0.002 mol) was cooled to -5° , then 2,3-

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butanedione (diacetyl) (0.002 mol) was added, stirred for 30 min and allowed to stand at room temperature. Then an ethanolic solution of the salt (0.001 mol) (except metal sulfate) was added to the orange solution, stirred for 4 h and the resulting coloured solid was washed with ethanol and dried over silica gel.

Cu^{II} complexes of BDAP : A mixture of ethanolic solution of benzil (0.002 mol), 1,2-diaminopropane (0.002 mol) and ethanolic solution of metal salt (0.001 mol) (except metal sulfate) was refluxed for 4 h. On cooling the solution overnight, the coloured complex that separated out was washed with ethanol and dried over silica gel.

The complexes were found soluble in DMSO.

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